

AGRONOMIC EVALUATION OF SOME ELITE CASSAVA GENOTYPES IN THE RAIN FOREST AGROECOLOGY OF SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Cassava (*Manihot esculentus*) is a first-ranking carbohydrate staple in Nigeria and is very popular in the food systems of the humid and subhumid agroecological areas. It has high potential needs with diverse utilization capacities. Unfortunately, the current annual output of the crop is very low due to the predominant use of local clones which are disease-prone with characteristically low yield potential. Authentic information on yield capacity of the recently released CMD-resistant genotypes is still lacking. This formed the basis of the study. The design of the trial was a randomized complete block (RCB) involving fifteen clones (96/1565, 96/1642, 96/1089A, 96/2205, 94/0561, 95/0289, 02/0026, 04/0026, 95/0379, 92B/00061, 94/0039, 97/3200, 91/02324 and 95/0166) and three checks (4(2) 1425, 82/00058 and TME 30572) as treatments, each replication four times. The experiment was set at the Crop Production Farm of the University of Calabar in 2004 and 2005 main cropping seasons. Cassava Mosaic Diseases (CMD) resistant clones were planted at 10,000 plants/ha in the first week of April each year and harvested after ten months of growth. Data collected were plant height (at harvest), total number and weight of marketable tubers/roots (weighing \geq 300g and \geq 20cm long), unmarketable tubers/roots (weighing < 300g and < 20cm long), per plot, foliage yield, and roots/tuber yield per hectare. Results obtained showed significant variations among the cultivars in all the parameters measured. Clones 96/1642, 96/0603 94/0561, 95/0289 and 92/0026 exhibited tall plant height like the check 82/0026, 97/3200 and 95/0166 produced high proportion of marketable tubers ranging from 45-75 per plot compared to the check TME 30572 with 52 of such roots/tuber per plot. Superior forage production capacity was demonstrated by 96/0603 and 94/0561 which produced 46.47 tons/ha and 41.67 tones/ha respectively while the highest root/tuber yield of 40-50 tones/ha was produced by the clones 97/2205, 96/0603, 95/0289 and TME 30572. It is concluded that most of the clones evaluated performed well with capacity to produce high quantities of forage to support livestock production. Cassava growers are therefore advised to source planting materials from clones 97/2205, 96/0603, 94/0039, 91/02324, 95/0289, 94/0026, 97/3200, 95/0166, TME30572 which have high tuber yield and high forage production capacity to generate additional revenue from the sale of forage/hay.

KEY WORDS: Agronomic evaluation, Cassava mosaic disease (CMD), Elite cassava genotypes, Rain forest agroecology, Root/forage yield, Southeastern Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculentus* var *utilissima*) is an important first ranking carbohydrate staple in Nigeria and has been integrated into the peasant production systems in the humid and subhumid agroecological areas (Onwueme, 1982). According to FAO (2002), the current annual cassava output of 345 million metric tones is grossly inadequate to meet the ever-increasing demand for the crop for human food, livestock feeds and for industrial purposes (IITA, 1998).

The presidential initiative on cassava which has brought to limelight the potentials of cassava as a foreign exchange earner has further widened the demand-supply gap of the crop. The existence of unsaturated markets for cassava has implications for sustainable approaches to step-up the production in the country. Increased cassava

output could be achieved through making available to farmers cultivars that are of high-yielding, disease-resistant early-maturing and have high dry matter and starch contents.

At the moment many of the cassava cultivars available to majority of Nigerian cassava growers are local clones which may have acceptable quality characteristics that meet the end-user's requirements for food but are characteristically low yield potential of only about 7-10 t/ha (Ohnuweme 1982; FAO 2002).

Recently, a number of early-maturing clones have been screened and certified resistant to the notorious cassava mosaic disease (CMD) that decimates yield of the crop in all its areas of cultivation. But baseline information on growth and yield performance of these clones is not yet available especially in Cross River State which is a major producer of the crop. The need to carryout some agronomic evaluation of some of these CMD varieties to provide such baseline information was the objective of this work.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted during the early planting of 2004 and 2005 cropping seasons at the Crop Research Farm of the University of Calabar (04°57'N and 08°21'E; 37 metres above sea level). The site was previously cropped to maize and melon and fallowed for two years before this experiment. The land was mechanically ploughed without clearing so that the vegetation was completely incorporated into the soil to improve the soil organic matter content. After one week, the entire field was reploughed to ensure complete destruction of weeds and demarcated into plots measuring 36m² (6mX6m).

The treatments were the fifteen CMD-resistant clones and three checks as follows: 96/1565 96/1642, 98/1089A, 97/2205, 96/0603,94/0561, 95/0289, 92/0067, 94/0026, 95/0379, 92B/00061, 94/0039, 973200, 91/02324, 95/0166, and the checks were 4(2) 145, 82/00058 and TMS 30572.

The planting materials were supplied by International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Innoe High Rainfall Station, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Cuttings were pre-sprouted in transparent polythene bags before planting on flats at 10,000 plants/ha in the first and several weeks of April for 2004 and 2005 planting respectively. Experimental plots were laid out in randomized complete block design (RCB) with four replications.

Plots were weeded manually two times before full development of the crop canopies. Lost stands were supplied to ensure complete crop stands in each plot. Chemical inputs were not applied and the crops grew as under farmers' fields.

All the plots were harvested after ten months of growth and tubers were classified into marketable tubers (tubers weighing \geq 300g and \geq 20cm long) and unmarketable tubers (tubers weighing $<$ 300g and $<$ 20cm long) the above classification was based on the IITA standard specification (IITA, 1990).

Relevant agronomic data collected from plants in the three inner rows in each plot were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique. Significant means were further separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) at 5% level of significance as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Root yield indices and foliage production potential varied significantly ($P=0.05$) among the cassava genotypes used (Table 1). Height attained by clones 96/1642, 96/0603, 94/0561, 950289, and 92/00026 was similar to that of the check clone 82/00058. These clones were significantly taller than all other clones which exhibited similar height with the other two checks (4(2) 1425 and TME 30572). Differences in plant height among the various cultivars could be attributed to their genetic diversity since they were grown under similar growing conditions. The height differences of the clones may present alternative choices to farmers based on their objective or priority of production. Farmers whose interest is commercial multiplication of planting materials would opt for tall clones with good root yield like 96/0603, 95/0289 and 92/0026 that have high potential to generate adequate planting stems. However, peasant producers would select or prefer dwarf cultivars with high root yield like 97/2205, 96/0166, 97/3200, 94/0039 and 96/1089A for effective weed suppression thereby reducing the need for frequent weeding and hence, reduce cost of production.

Tuber characteristics evaluated in terms of marketable and unmarketable tubers also varied significantly among the clones and checks. Clones 97/2205, 96/0603, 94/0039 and 91/02324 produced more marketable tubers per plot than TME 30572 that produced the highest number of this type of tubers among the check clones (Table 1). Apart from the clone 94/0561 which was least in marketable tubers all other clones were similar to the check 4(2)1425 in this parameter. On the other hand, significantly more unmarketable or inferior tubers were produced by clones 94/0379, 96/1089A and 91/0224 similar to the check 82/0058 while 94/0561, 92B/00061 produced few of these tubers per plot like the check clone 4(2)1425.

It has been reported that tuber formation in cassava depends on a number of factors include soil type, land preparation and growing conditions as well as the genetic potential of the clone (Ekanayake, *et al*, 1998).

The choice of clones to cultivate depends on the marketing strategy to be adopted by producers. Farmers who intend to market unprocessed tubers prefer genotypes that produce optimum tubers which are easily marketed. Such producers are interested in size, shape and weight of tubers as large, smooth and heavy tubers are presentable with high aesthetic and economic value and are usually preferred by buyers irrespective of their dry matter content. In this regards clones such as 96/0603, 97/2205, 95/0289, 92/0026, 97/3200, 95/0166, 91/02324, 94/0039 and TME 30572 which produced a high proportion of marketable tubers would score high among cassava growers/marketers.

The capacity of the tested clones to produce forage for livestock feeds varied among them with clones 96/0603 and 94/0561 being superior to all other clones in this parameter. However, such clones as 96/1642, 97/2205, 95/0289, 92/02324, 95/0166 and TME 30572 also produced appreciably high quantities of forage ranging from 20-30 tones/ha.

Cassava leaves have been reported to be an excellent source of high quality forage material (IITA, 1998). Apart from the clone 94/0561 which produced more foliage (41.67 tones/ha) than tubers (25.44 tones/ha), other high forage yielding clones also have very high tuber yield especially clones 96/0603 which yielded 46.47 tones/ha and 50.72 tones/ha of forage and fresh tubers respectively.

Since availability of browse material for ruminants is always a problem in the dry season, cassava growers in the areas where livestock are kept on commercial scale can take advantage of these cultivars to produce hay for commercial purposes in order to earn additional revenue.

A comparison of the foliage and tuber production of the various clones revealed that clones 97/2205 and 95/0166 have low forage yield but highly efficient in tuber formation. Also tuber yield performance of clone 94/0561 is quite low compared to its high foliage productivity. However, good tuber yield and high foliage production qualities and can serve as a dual or multipurpose cultivars for more economic benefits to the farmers.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

The cassava genotypes evaluated varied in tuber and forage yield. Clones 97/2205 and 95/0166 clearly exhibited high tuber yield and low forage production potential while clone 94/0561 showed high forage productivity. However, clones 96/0603, 94/0039, 91/02324, 95/0289, 91/0026, 97/3200, 96/1642 and TME 30572 combined high capacity for tuber and forage productivity. The dual or multipurpose clones are highly recommended to cassava growers for maximum economic benefit.

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Table 1: Growth and teuber yield indices of some selected CMD-resistant cassava clones grown in Ultisol (Mean values for 2004/2005 cropping seasons)

Clone	Plant ht (m)	Number of tubers/plot		Total No of tubers/plot	Total wt (kg) of tubers/plot	Wt (Kg) of marketable tubers/plot	Forage yield (t/ha)	Tuber yield (t/ha)
		Marketable	Unmarketable					
96/1565	1.65	49.26	36.75	76.00	22.65	18.85	12.06	25.17
96/1642	2.06	49.75	49.60	98.50	25.93	20.85	23.33	28.81
4(2)1425	1.76	32.75	14.25	47.00	23.45	21.05	10.00	26.06
96/1089A	1.63	45.75	40.00	65.75	29.80	22.40	18.88	33.11
97/2205	1.98	56.00	41.25	97.25	36.23	30.60	25.94	40.26
96/0603	2.48	75.00	29.25	104.25	45.65	42.95	46.47	50.72
94/0561	2.65	27.25	17.00	51.75	22.90	20.58	41.67	25.44
95/0289	2.50	44.50	31.50	76.00	36.08	32.60	31.44	40.09
92/0026	2.30	48.50	26.00	74.50	37.30	34.00	9.17	41.44
82/00058	3.13	49.75	52.00	102.00	30.80	24.15	26.89	334.22
94/0026	1.95	46.25	33.00	79.25	18.85	15.75	16.17	20.94
95/0339	1.93	41.75	40.50*	87.25	21.00	15.75	20.39	23.33
92B/00061	1.58	45.50	18.75	64.00	28.35	26.53	14.17	31.50
914/0039	1.78	62.25	55.75*	14.00	31.90	27.30	21.37	35.44
97/3200	1.91	49.00	31.25	80.25	33.65	30.20	17.64	37.38
91/02324	1.61	71.50	52.00	123.50	29.68	25.90	20.22	32.98
95/0166	1.68	60.50	22.75	83.25	40.50	37.48	24.17	45.00
TME 30575	1.73	52.25	41.00	93.25	22.10	17.75	24.56	24.56
LSD (0.05)	0.45	24.60	20.80	35.50	8.36	15.20	8.94	10.12

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